

Liquids Analysis with Optofluidic Bragg Microcavities

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Abstract

Porous Bragg microcavities formed by stacking porous nanocolumnar layers of different refraction index materials (SiO₂ and TiO₂) have been prepared by physical vapor deposition at glancing angles (GLAD) and their optical properties tuned by changing the thickness and the evaporation angle of the TiO₂ and SiO₂ layers. By strictly controlling the porosity and refraction index of the individual films, as well as the relative orientation of the nanocolumns from one layer to the other, it has been possible to manufacture very porous and high optical quality microcavities. These structures have been implemented into responsive devices to characterize liquids, mixtures of liquids or solutions flowing through them. The large displacements observed in the

optical spectral features (Bragg reflector gap and resonant peak) of the photonic structures have been quantitatively correlated with the refraction index of the circulating liquids. Experiments carried out with different glucose and NaCl solutions and mixtures water plus glycerol illustrate the potentialities of these materials acting as optofluidic devices to determine the concentration of solutions or the proportion of two phases in a liquid mixture.

KEYWORDS: Bragg porous microcavities, Optofluidics, TiO₂, SiO₂, GLAD thin films, liquid microsensors.

1. Introduction

Responsive systems are devices or materials capable of responding automatically in a predictable and reversible way to an external physical or chemical stimulus from the environment.¹ For chemical analysis, such systems may substitute complex analytical instruments and provide simple and reliable procedures for the detection or even the determination of the concentration of a given analyte in a mixture with other components.²⁻⁴ The physical parameters that can be modified by interaction with the environment can be of different nature and affect the optical, electrical or even magnetic properties of the material or device. A simple example based on changes in optical parameters refers to the variations produced in the refractive index of porous thin films or multilayer structures when they are exposed to vapors of water or other condensable compounds.⁵ Similar changes in the optical response are the basis of the emerging field of Optofluidic,⁶ where changes in the optical properties of many devices (e.g., wave guides, stacked multilayer or other photonic structures) are reversibly

controlled by the incorporation of liquids. Optical lattices with controlled and accessible porosity has been utilized for chemical responsive applications with systems made by the stacking of metal oxide nanoparticles, ^{7,8} mesostructured thin films, ^{9,10} clays, ¹¹ macroporous alumina ¹² or porous silicon layers. ^{5, 13, 14} In this line, we have recently shown that multilayer structures prepared by physical vapor deposition in the form of one-dimensional photonic crystals (1DPC) may experience a large change in the position of their wide transmission gap when they are infiltrated with liquids.¹⁵ A similar effect has been recently proposed for the identification of solvents by using 1DPC formed by the stacking of polymer layers and titania nanoparticles.¹⁶ A 1DPC, also known as Bragg stack or Bragg reflecting mirror, is a simple photonic structure made by the stacking of successive and alternating layers of two transparent materials with different refractive index. Due to optical interference processes, these photonic structures produce a reflection of light that extends over a certain range (Bragg gap) of wavelengths producing the impression of a colored mirror. The position and width of the reflecting gap can be tuned by controlling the number of stacking layers, their thickness and the difference in the refractive index of the two materials.

Planar Bragg microcavities, a modification of 1DPCs, integrate in the center of a Bragg reflector a layer with a different thickness. The incorporation of this layer, considered as an optical defect, gives rise to the appearance of a resonance narrow peak in the Bragg gap. Planar Bragg microcavities made of porous silicon prepared by electrochemical methods have been proposed for sensing vapours^{5, 13, 14} or for the development of advanced biosensing tests.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ The integration of a non-planar Bragg microcavity fabricated by electron-beam lithography and reactive ion etching techniques into a microfluid device for optofluidic applications has been reported recently.²⁰

In the present work we report the fabrication of planar Bragg microcavities by stacking successive layers of two transparent and porous oxides prepared by e-beam evaporation in a glancing angle configuration (GLAD).¹⁵ This geometrical configuration renders films formed by tilted nanocolumns with a considerable amount of void space in the form of meso- and micro-pores (i.e., pores larger or smaller than 2nm according to the IUPAC, ²¹). A full account of the pores and other characteristics of this type of thin films can be found in recent publications.²²⁻²⁴ GLAD thin films have been also deposited to modify the channel walls of microfluidic devices to facilitate the circulation of liquids ²⁵ or to provide high surface area substrates to increase the anchoring capacity of active molecules used for molecular recognition.²⁶ However, no essays have been reported about the direct use of GLAD thin film structures as microfluidic components, a fact that is likely related to the difficulty of accurately controlling the porosity and optical properties of both the individual GLAD thin films and the collective response of the final microcavities. A first objective of the present work is to prove that the optical properties of porous GLAD microcavities can be accurately controlled without incurring in light dispersion effects very common when dealing with other type of porous materials. Subsequently, we show that these porous structures can be integrated in the form of planar microfluidic components through which liquids can circulate easily. Using this configuration we show that planar Bragg microcavities, made by stacking several porous TiO₂ and SiO₂ GLAD thin films, can be used as efficient optofluidic responsive systems for measuring the solute concentrations of liquid solutions or for the analysis of liquid mixtures. Case examples of the response of these devices and the modeling of their optical response by using a conventional interference optical model²⁷ complete the present work.

2. Experimental and Methods

Uniform, mechanically stable and highly porous Bragg microcavity structures made of alternated layers of TiO_2 and SiO_2 with a thicker SiO_2 central layer have been prepared by glancing angle physical vapour deposition (GLAD). Porous layers were successively e-beam evaporated on glass plates of $1.2 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ at glancing zenithal angles of 70° and 80° (α). SiO_2 and TiO_2 were used as target materials while an oxygen pressure of approximately 10^{-4} torr was kept in the chamber during the evaporation to ensure the complete oxidation of the evaporated oxides (i.e. to get TiO_2 and SiO_2 stoichiometries) and hence their full transparency (TiO_x or SiO_x with $x < 2$ are colored). The GLAD geometry produces films with a characteristic tilted columnar morphology which is controlled by shadowing effects. [22]. The results reported here refer to structures consisting of 2×7 individual layers of approximately 85 nm thickness, plus one SiO_2 middle layer of approximately 180 nm thickness. The thickness of each individual layer was controlled by means of a quartz crystal monitor calibrated with the actual thickness of layers determined by cross section SEM.

Preparations were carried out by azimuthally turning the substrate 90° when changing the evaporation from one oxide to the other. Turning azimuthally the substrate between two layers is required to avoid the dispersion of light, an effect that has been previously addressed in a work on porous 1DPC used to prepare dye sensitized solar cells.²⁸

The stacked layers deposited on a glass plate were sandwiched with another glass plate provided with two holes where liquid tubes acting as inlet/outlet channels of the fluids were fixed. The perimeter of the ensemble was sealed with PDMS to ensure the tightness of the system. A scheme of the system is presented in **Figure 1**, together with

a view of a real device fabricated in the course of this work. In this device, the space between the two glass plates is completely filled with the microcavity structure and the fluids flow by passing through the pores of the films by just applying a small pressure difference between the inlet and outlet tubes. It could be also realized that liquids with low viscosity and surface tension can pass spontaneously driven by capillarity forces. This configuration ensures that pores are completely filled with the liquid and that an easy and immediate replacement of one liquid by another is possible by just changing an external reservoir connected to the device. Another important clue, proved by simulating²⁷ the optical response of the system, was that no empty space is left between the stacked microcavity and the glass cover plate.

Figure 1.- (left) Cross section scheme and (right) image of an optofluidic device based on a Bragg microcavity prepared by GLAD. Note that the different parts in the scheme are not plotted at the same scale.

Cross section SEM micrographs were obtained in a Hitachi S4800 field emission microscope for samples deposited on a silicon wafer that were cleaved for cross section analysis.

UV-vis transmission spectra were recorded in normal and off-normal configurations with a Cary 100 instrument. For recording at off-normal angles, the optofluidic device

was turned with respect to the light beam by using a goniometer provided with a holding piece.

Simulation of the optical response of the Bragg microcavity was done by optimized fitting of the transmittance spectra using a home-made code based on the transfer-matrix approach. Typical Cauchy dispersion was considered for the refractive index. The refractive index and the thicknesses of the SiO₂ and TiO₂ layers in the two 7-layers Bragg reflectors and the SiO₂ defect layer were obtained through the fitting procedure.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Microstructure and optical properties of Bragg microcavities prepared by GLAD

Figure 2 shows a cross section SEM micrograph of a GLAD porous Bragg microcavity integrated by two Bragg reflectors made of 7 stacked layers of SiO₂ and TiO₂ sandwiching a thicker SiO₂ layer as indicated by the diagram of the figure. The thickness of the SiO₂ and TiO₂ stacked layers was about 80 nm, while that of the SiO₂ defect was around 180 nm. An accurate control of the optical properties of the microcavity was possible by changing these thickness dimensions. The whole structure was prepared by GLAD at a fixed zenithal angle of $\alpha=70^\circ$ by turning the substrate 90° from one layer to the next. This azimuthal rotation was essential to decrease the dispersion of light at low wavelengths, a common phenomenon found for relatively thick GLAD oxide films. Similar structures were grown by performing the evaporation at a zenithal angle of 80° . The SEM micrograph of an 80° microcavity and a scheme of the relative orientation of the nanocolumns in each layer of the structure resulting from the 90° azimuthal rotation are reported as supporting information (**S1**).

It is worth stressing that compared with conventional silicon porous Bragg microcavities prepared by controlled electrochemical oxidation followed by annealing at high temperature, ^{5,13,14,17-19} the GLAD methodology is advantageous because it is compatible with any sensitive substrate (e.g. polymers) and does not require any oxidation step at high temperatures to make the stacked layers transparent. Moreover, the large contrast between the refractive index of the individual SiO₂ and TiO₂ layers of the GLAD microcavities (SiO₂ and TiO₂ GLAD layers have refractive indices of 1.22/1.20 and 1.70/1.55 when prepared at 70° and 80°, respectively^{22, 23}) and their high pore volume (i.e., approximately 49% and 60% for these two evaporation angles^{22, 23}) make these optical devices suitable for a wide range of optofluidic applications.

Figure 2.(top) cross section SEM micrograph (bright and dark fields) of a cleaved microcavity prepared by evaporation at 70° of zenithal angle. The scheme shows the stacking order of the individual layers forming the microcavity. (Bottom) UV-vis transmission spectra of microcavities prepared at 70° (left) and 80° (right) zenithal angles. Simulated spectra are plotted for comparison.

The optical behaviour of the microcavity structure was checked by UV-vis transmission spectroscopy. **Figure 2** (bottom) shows the measured and simulated transmission spectra obtained for microcavities prepared at 70° and 80° of zenithal angle of evaporation. These spectra depict the typical behavior of planar optical microcavities

which, for the 70° case, consists of a wide reflecting region extending from approximately 500 to 700 nm, and a narrow and sharp resonant peak located at 579 nm and a width at half height of 18.5 nm (i.e. a Q factor, defined as the ratio of the resonance cavity frequency to the line width of the cavity mode, of 31). For the 80° microcavity, these spectral parameters are 486, and 23.7 nm (Q factor 20), respectively. In this latter case the position and other spectral features of the transmission spectra are well reproduced for $\lambda > 450$ nm, but deviations are observed below this wavelength value. We attribute the decrease in the transmitted light in this spectral region, enhanced at high zenithal angles, to light dispersion effects at the void and oxide material nanostructures formed in these films.^{5, 28}

For the individual layers, Table 1 summarizes the thickness values determined experimentally by SEM and those estimated by the simulation of the spectral features. The refractive index values of SiO₂ and TiO₂ required to get a good fitting are also included in this table. Within a variation of 10%, limit of accuracy estimated for the simulations, the calculated refractive indices are similar to the experimental values of **n** previously determined for GLAD thin films of these materials.^{22,23} In comparison with the **n** values of compact films of these two oxides (i.e., around 1.45 and 2.40 for SiO₂ and TiO₂, respectively²⁹), the low value of this parameter obtained for the GLAD thin films confirms their high porosity and, hence, the possibility of modifying **n** if the pores are filled with liquids. The porosity values of the individual layers of the Bragg microcavity determined by simulation are reported in Table 1.

3.2 Optofluidic response of microcavities

To check whether the optical response of the GLAD microcavities changes when their pores are filled with a fluid, we flowed a series of liquids of different refraction indices

through a microfluidic device integrating the Bragg porous structure. **Figure 3** shows the experimental and simulated UV-vis transmission spectra obtained for an empty 70° microcavity and after circulating through it liquids of different refractive indices (i.e., water ($n=1.330$), ethanol ($n=1.361$), toluene ($n=1.496$) and chlorobenzene ($n=1.525$)). An observed effect is a shift to longer wavelengths of both the transmission gap and of the resonant peak. The magnitude of the shifts depends on the refractive index of the liquid and can be simulated by varying the effective refractive indices of each individual layer attacked in the microcavity. The values obtained for the case of water are gathered in **Table 1**, while the values deduced for the other liquids are reported in the supporting information (**Table S2**). The calculated refractive indices are higher than those of the empty (actually air-filled) layers as expected for a medium consisting of a liquid filling the pores and voids of the individual films microstructure.

Figure 3. Experimental (full lines) and simulated (dashed lines) UV-vis transmission spectra of a microcavity device prepared at 70° before (black line) and after (gray lines) circulating different liquids through it: a), water; b), ethanol; c), toluene; d) Chlorobenzene. The vertical lines indicate the position of the resonant peak in the microcavity without any liquid (i.e., with the pores filled with air).

Table 1.-Characteristic layer parameters of Bragg microcavities prepared at $\alpha=70^\circ$ and 80° . Thickness and refractive index values are derived from the SEM measurements (exp) and by simulation of the transmission spectra (sim). Data are provided for the “as prepared” microcavities and for the microcavities integrated in an optofluidic device with water circulating through them.

Zenithal angle/layer	Thickness (exp) (nm)	Thickness (sim) (nm)	n (sim)	n with water (sim)	Porosity (sim) (%)
70° TiO ₂	94	88	1.69	1.83	49
70° SiO ₂	88	81	1.23	1.39	49
70° SiO ₂ defect	224	178	1.21	1.39	52
80° TiO ₂	82	88	1.55	1.72	60
80° SiO ₂	80	86	1.20	1.38	55
80° SiO ₂ defect	168	180	1.20	1.38	55

A similar behavior was observed for the microcavities prepared at 80°, with the additional effect that the transmission at low wavelengths recovered the level predicted

by the theoretical simulation. This effect is attributed to the removal of light scattering effects by the liquids infiltrated through the otherwise empty micro- and meso-pores (see **Figure S3** in supporting information).

The overall optical changes induced by circulating liquids through the microcavity devices were so apparent that they could be observed with the bare eyes (c.f. **Figure 4** (left)), thus opening the possibility of using them as visual tags.

Figure 4. (left) Images of 70° and 80° microfluidic devices empty (top) and filled with toluene (bottom). (right) Plot of the position of the resonant peak in the UV-vis spectra of the 70° and 80° microcavity devices as a function of the refractive index of the infiltrated liquid.

From an analytical point of view it is quite significant that the shift in the position of the resonant peak observed in **Figures 3** and **S3** can be directly related to the refractive index of the infiltrated liquid as reported in **Figure 4** (right). This plot shows that the position of the maximum of the resonant peak varies almost linearly with the refractive index of the infiltrated liquid and supports that this kind of optofluidic device can be

used to identify liquids of different refractive indices. A similar approach has been used to detect vapors of organic solvents by means of Bragg microcavities made of porous silicon layers of different porosities.^{5,15,16}

A well-known behavior of compact Bragg microcavities is an angular dispersion in the position of the resonance peak when varying the incident angle of light.²⁷ As reported in **Figure 5**, porous microcavities behave in the same way either empty or filled with a liquid. This figure clearly shows that the resonant peak position shifts to shorter wavelengths when tilting the device with respect to the direction of light. Similar shifts were also observed for 80° microcavity structures (see **Figure S4** in the supporting information). Within the angular variation monitored in this experiment, the resonance peak kept a similar height and width irrespective of the incident angle of light.

Figure 5. UV-vis transmission spectra for the indicated incident angles of light for an empty (left) and a water infiltrated (right) 70° microcavity structure.

Similar angular variations were found for the porous microcavities filled with liquids (c.f., **Figure 5** (right)), although the magnitude of the shift depended on the refraction index of the liquid. For example, turning by 40° the 70° microcavity, resulted in a shift of 53 nm for the empty device and 48 and 54nm for the system filled with water or

chlorobenzene, respectively. Similar effects could be appreciated for the microcavities prepared at 80° (see Figure S4 in the supporting information).

3.4 Optofluidic analysis of liquid solutions by means of GLAD microcavities

The previous sections have dealt with the change in the optical response of porous microcavities when they are infiltrated with pure liquids. Due to the large difference in the refractive index of the porous TiO₂ and SiO₂ constituent layers, the microcavity device structures were very sensitive to small differences in the refractive index of the infiltrated liquids. Taking advantage of this enhanced sensitivity we propose to use these microcavities to determine the concentration of liquid solutions or the proportion of two liquids in a mixture. Some proofs of concept will be reported here to ascertain the feasibility of this analytical approach.

Figure 6 shows a series of UV-vis spectra in the region of the resonance peak for a 70° microcavity circulated with NaCl and glucose solutions with concentrations ranging from 0.5 to 4 mol/l and 0.5 to 3 mol/l, respectively. The spectra show that the peak position steadily varies with the solution concentration, a dependence that must be attributed to the different refraction index of the solutions.³⁰ Moreover, a representation of the peak position versus the solution concentrations yields in the two cases a practically linear dependence. These lines can be taken as calibration curves of glucose and NaCl concentrations for this particular device.

Figure 6.-(left) UV-vis transmission spectra for a 70° microcavity infiltrated with water and a series NaCl (a) and glucose (c) solutions of the indicated concentrations. Right) Plots of the shift in the position of the resonance peak as a function of NaCl (b) and glucose (d) concentrations. Note the different scales used for each plot.

Monitoring the peak position requires a wavelength sensitive detector. Since intensity detectors are simpler, cheaper and easier to operate, we explored an alternative way of measuring the solute concentration by looking to the angular variation of the peak position (cf. **Figures 6** and **S4**) as a function of the solute concentration. The principle of the measuring procedure is reported in **Figure 7**, illustrated for the case of 70° microcavity, empty and filled with water. For a 0° incident angle of light, the resonance peak shifts to longer wavelengths when the device is infiltrated with water. This shift can be counterbalanced by turning the optofluidic device by an angle of 49° with respect to the light beam direction. For practical purposes, measurements of solution

concentrations would be possible by using a single wavelength source (e.g. a LED) tuned to the resonance maximum of the microcavity, either empty or filled with water, an intensity detector and a goniometer to measure the angular shift required to recover the maximum intensity of the transmitted light.

Figure 7.-(Top) Scheme showing the variation of the position of the resonant peak when a microcavity is filled with water and the recovery of the initial wavelength position when the device is turned by a given angle. (Bottom) Correlation between the turned angles of the microcavity and the concentration of the NaCl and glucose solutions according to the procedure described in the scheme.

For the investigated NaCl and glucose solutions, **Figure 7** shows the angular variations obtained as a function of the solution concentrations. Although the dependence is not linear, the depicted profiles follow well-defined calibration curves that can be used to determine the concentration of unknown solutions of these two substances.

Mixtures of liquids with different refractive indices can be also monitored by using GLAD microcavity devices, provided that they present sufficiently large differences of refractive indices. **Figure 8** shows the results obtained for mixtures of glycerol ($n=1.473$) and water ($n =1.330$). The spectra and the plot in this figure are referred to the volume percentage of glycerol. It is apparent in this figure that the resonant peak shifts with the percentage of glycerol and that this shift follows well defined dependences, both when representing the wavelength of the maximum of the resonant peak or the angle turned to recover its maximum intensity. These results clearly prove that an optofluidic device consisting of a porous microcavity prepared by GLAD can be used to determine the proportion of two liquids in a mixture, provided that their refraction indices differ sufficiently.

Figure 7.-(left) UV-vis transmission spectra for a 70° microcavity infiltrated with mixtures of glycerol and water with different proportions of the two liquids. (Right) Plot of the shift in the position of the resonance peak and angle turned to restore its maximum intensity as a function of percentage of glycerol in the mixture.

Besides these simple applications, we anticipate that this type of devices will be useful for the continuous monitoring of liquids in microfluidic³¹ or other analytical applications involving minutes amounts of liquids (the pore volume of a microcavity device can be estimated in $\sim 7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^3$) or as cheap disposable systems for food control. As practical cases of this latter application field, Figures **S5 and S6** of the supporting information report two examples showing how the developed microcavities can identify common beverages (different types of colas, isotonic drinks, etc.) or vegetable oils (e.g., olive or sunflower oils). Even if the viscosity of oils is rather high, its management through the microcavity structures is quite straightforward, what opens the way to the practical implementation of these devices for the analysis of a large variety of liquids.

4. Conclusions

In this work we have shown that it is possible to manufacture planar porous microcavities by electron-beam GLAD of successive layers of two oxides (SiO_2 and TiO_2) of different refraction indices. A strategy consisting of azimuthally turning the substrate from one layer to the next has been developed to minimize the light scattering

effects usually observed for thick porous layers. These microcavities have resulted very useful to determine the refraction index of liquids and solutions. The high transparency of the individual constituent layers and their high porosity have prompted us to try their integration in the form of an optofluidic device where liquids fill and circulate through their open porosity. The simulation analysis of the changes observed in the transmission spectra of the microcavities after infiltration has proved that the position of the resonance peak depends on the refraction index of the liquid. This feature has been used systematically to determine the characteristics of the liquids by both measuring the position of the maximum or by turning the photonic structure by a certain angle to restore the maximum intensity of the resonance peak at its initial wavelength. These two methods of detection have been successfully used to determine the concentration of different solutions and mixtures of liquids.

The low volume of liquid required to induce these changes makes that the developed technology can be easily implemented into complex microfluidic systems where it could provide a simple and reliable method of analysis. In addition they could be employed as switchable optofluidic components for photonic applications.

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